

**BUKHARA OF ZARAFSHAN OASIS AT THE END OF THE XIX
CENTURY AND THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURY
HANDICRAFTS AND TRADE - SALES IN THEIR RESPECTIVE AREAS
OF THE EMIRATES**

Jumaev Bekzod

researcher of Termiz State University

Abstract. In the lower part of the Zarafshan oasis, that is, in the central part of the Bukhara Emirate Bukhara, Gijduvan, Vobkent, Pirmast, Khoja under its control Arif (Shofirkon), Romitan and Zarafshan (North and South Rud) districts⁴² and in the regions of Karakol, Karmana and Ziyavuddin densely lived.

Key words. Bukhara, Gijduvan, Vobkent, Pirmast, Khoja Arif (Shofirkon), Romitan, Zarafshan, Karakol, Karmana, Ziyavuddin.

Uzbeks make up the majority of the population of the Lower Zarafshan Valley and Tajiks, tribes and peoples speaking Turkic and Iranian languages in 1924- in the oasis and its surroundings due to the research conducted in Central Asia the preliminary report on the number and ethnic composition of the living population information is obtained. According to this information, lower Zarafshan The total area of the oasis is 2,832 sq.km., and the population is 359,118 consisted of people. The area of the Karakol region is 712 sq. km 24765 people, area of Karmana region (excluding Qarnab desert) 3253 It is also noted that the population consists of 82,990 people. Oasis most of the population (86.8%) lived in rural areas. Ethnic composition Uzbeks (284,753 people), Tajiks (39,044 people), Arabs (31,541 people) and Turkmens (12,773 people) made up the majority.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the population was divided into different clans standing For example, people who lived in Shafirkon region are divided into

14 clans divided, the population of Vobkent is 26, the population of Romitan is 15, the population of Karakol is 32, The population of Gijduvan is 38, the population of Karmana is 33, and around Bukhara (in Galasia) the population belonged to 38 clans and ethnic groups. The population according to the results of registration, the clan is not divided into tribes Among the living Uzbeks, the Chigatays were a significant minority.

In particular, 230 people in the oasis near Bukhara, around Shafirkon On the banks of the Sultanrabort brook and the Shahrud brook in the Galaasia area 210 people of Chigatoy lived there. 565 in Karakol people considered themselves to belong to the Chigatai clan. Once upon a time the steppe descendants of Uzbeks who migrated from Kipchak gained considerable influence in the lower Zarafshan oasis.

Special among them Mangits (44,000 people) who have a position are located in the northern part of the oasis in Shafirkon, Gijduvan and Romiton regions on the north-eastern side I was satisfied. There are also 8,000 mangits in the Karakol oasis

registered. According to the information of Mirza Badi Devon, the mangists they themselves are divided into parts. For example, black, white, blue separated.

At the beginning of the 16th century, bells came to the oasis and settled in Bukhara and A large number of clans (13,875 people in total) in the Karakol region calculated. Also with Kyzylkum in the north of Gijdivan Border settlements and Shofirkonda (5245 people), Sultanrabort stream (2370 people) and on the banks of the Vobkent river (2160 people). the bells lived. Saray clan is also in Uzbek clans took one of the leading places. Representatives of this clan are different from the oasis lived scattered throughout the territories. Most of the palaces are Harkhonrud

17,945 people along the banks of the river, including 7,095 people in the Gijdivan region, 4165 people in Vobkent, 3575 people along Shahrud creek and Sultanabad

1310 people on the banks of the stream, partly on the banks of the Pirmast stream (Gijdivan in the area), in Abu Muslim (in the areas of Kogon and Kiziltepa) and Poykent (in the Karakol region) was scattered.

The representatives of the Katagon clan (7315 people in total) are mostly from the oasis Sultanabad (1,680), Pirmast (1,070) in the northern and northwestern parts nafar), Harkhonrud (995) and other small streams in Gijdivan area (2100 people) lived in their area. It is a network of repressions Alchins are located in the city of Bukhara and its surroundings, mainly in Harkhonrud and Along the Mozarongan ditches (1775 people), Kasaba in Karmana oasis and Those located along the Kalkanota ditches (750 people), Jaloir (1820 people), A small number of Uzbek clans, such as Kenagas (2725 people) and Bahrin (1390) until the beginning of the 20th century, Uzbek and Tajik languages were spoken locally intermingled with peoples, as well as the entire lower Zarafshan 16,140 people of mixed ethnicity called metis according to the oasis representatives of the groups are also registered, and they are mainly located in the suburbs of Bukhara, They lived in Kogon and Kiziltepa regions.

Steppe of origin in the northern and partly central parts of the oasis it was possible to meet other Uzbek clans from Kipchak. Including nines (5000) thousands (1413) forties and hundreds (9 185 people) are among them. The total number of Kipchaks is 9935 most of them are Shahrud (4970 people), Vobkent Darya (2105 people) and In the basin of Shafirikon ditches (1700 people), a minority lived scattered in the southern regions of the oasis. On the west side of the oasis 2170 species lived in Khayrabad basin. this seed representatives in Karmana (1565 people) and Karakol (1765 people) regions was spread.

The speech of the inhabitants who lived in the lower part of the Zarafshan oasis M. Mirzayev, who conducted philological research on the 1926 zoning an attempt to create an ethnographic map of the area based on the data did According to M. Mirzayev, the inhabitants of the lower part of the oasis divided into 4 groups

according to dialects:

1. Qarluq-Chigil-Uighur dialect Uzbek-speaking groups;
2. Uzbeks who speak the Oghuz dialect;
3. Uzbeks who speak the Kipchak dialect;
4. Uzbek (Qarluq-Chigil-Uighur dialect) and Tajik-speaking bilingual groups.

The Oguz dialect is mainly spoken in Karakol, Olot districts and Romiton in some villages of the district, namely Sepota, Korali, Vobkenda Chandir in the village, in the villages of Khargush, Khomin, and Khumdonak near Bukhara the inhabitants spoke. Uzbek clans that speak this dialect mainly alot, bayot, jigachi, dargali, karavul, sayot, salir, ersari, chandir, Old, Tamjik, Burjik and other clans were formed. In Kipchak dialect They spoke in some villages of Karmana. In Uzbek and Tajik and the speaking population is Mangit, Urganji, Naiman considered to be from their clans.

During these periods, some local villages in the oasis have only one population it is characterized by the fact that it consists of people belonging to the clan. Thus, in the second half of the 19th century, it was complicated in the Zarafshan oasis ethnodemographic processes took place. First of all, the population is huge increased, and secondly, a small number of ethnic groups were partially absorbed into the Uzbeks went, and thirdly, the arrival of Russian-speaking population representatives during this period observed. As a result, the ethnic composition of the population of the Zarafshan oasis is increasingly diverse it got dark.

The natural, geographical and climatic conditions of the Zarafshan oasis are not only for the population economic activity and lifestyle, but also multifaceted spiritual culture and became an important factor in the formation of the characteristics of the national psyche.

REFERENCES:

1. G o l o s o v D . Pokhod v Khivu v 1839. russknx voysk pod in the detachment nachalstvom Adjutant General Perovsky. "Military Collection", 1863. S.70.

2. Grishfeld V., Galkin M.N. Military - statisticheskoe opisanie Khiva oasis. Ch 11. -T., 1903.
3. Grodekov N. I. Khivinsky pokhod in 1873. Daystvia Caucasian detachment. Izdanie redaktsii ist. Journal. "Russkaya starina". S. 7–10.
4. Ignatev N. Mission in Khiva and Bukhara in 1858. S.-Petersburg. Gosudarstvennaya typography. 1897 g. P.135-136.
5. "Engineering Journal", 1874, No. 1. Similarly, Zièev H. in Turkestan Struggle against Russian aggression and domination (XVIII-early XX centuries). T., East. 1998. B.314.